

THE THREE TRAITS OF PERSONALITY AND THEIR IMPACT ON COMMITMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Dark Triad is a set of personality traits that includes Machiavellianism, Narcissism, and Psychopathy. In this case, Machiavellianism is characterised by exploitation and manipulation, distrust, a lack of morality, and a focus on self-interest and deception. A narcissist is a relatively stable individual who exhibits lavishness, self-love, and grandiose self-views. Asocial conduct, impulsivity, callousness, selfishness, and remorselessness are all features of psychopathy. Organizational commitment, but at the other hand, is an employee's psychological link to the workplace, which includes loyalty, job involvement, and acceptance of organisational principles. Data was collected from 180 private sector employees using standardised questionnaires. Machiavellism was found to have a negative association with organisational commitment.

Keywords: Machiavellianism, Narcissism, Psychopath, Organization Commitment

INTRODUCTION

The current study examines the impact of the Dark Triad personality type, which includes three traits: Machiavellianism, Narcissism, and Psychopathy, on employee job commitment. Individuals with a high score on the attributes are said to have "dark" qualities. Machiavellians are people who are manipulative, dishonest, exploit others, disregard morality, and are self-centered. They are "Master manipulators," according to Jones & Paulhus (2002), and may deceive anyone before they realise they have been defrauded of anything significant. Narcissists have fairly stable personalities that are characterised by self-centeredness, lavishness, and exaggerated self-perceptions (Morf and Rhodewalt 2001, Campbell 2005). The Self, self-regulatory methods, and interpersonal interactions are the three components of a narcissist. In every connection, they strive to find opportunities to gain attention and appreciation, boast, take credit from others, and play games. They are filled with positive life satisfaction and a high sense of self-esteem as a result of their achievement (Sedikides & Gregg et al., 2004). When they are unsuccessful, they display signs of aggressiveness, sadness, and anxiety (Bushman & Baumeister, 1998). (Campbell, Hoffman & Marchisio, 2011). Finally, psychopaths are antisocial individuals who act with impulsivity, greed, insensitivity, and brutality. They are "arguably the most evil," according to Paulhus (2009), with greater scores on callous attitude, impulsiveness, manipulation, and grandiosity. Because they are members of the evil triad, they frequently damage others because they are only concerned with themselves when they are high on adrenaline.

The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of the dark triad on organisational commitment. In recent organisational psychology literature, the concept of

commitment has grown in prominence. The first studies on organisational commitment were one-dimensional, focusing on attitudinal perspective, self-identity, involvement, and loyalty (Porter et al, 1974). It is a person's psychological contract or emotional commitment to the organisation with which he is associated. It is an employee's connection to the organisation based on how similar his own beliefs, aims, and values are to those of the organisation for which he works (Cohen,2003).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This study focuses on the impact of the Dark Triad personality trait group, which includes psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism, on employee job commitment. As a result, literature on all three traits is evaluated in order to provide insight for the current investigation. Machiavelli's are crafty personnel who are deceptive, cruel, and disloyal to the organisations for which they work. They are the dark triadic persons in the organisation, according to Oliver James (2013), with others being psychopaths and narcissists. Studies have shown that high machismo leaders are less engaged to their jobs, resulting in a higher departure rate (Wilson et al., 1994). There are both positive and negative relationship ideologies when it comes to their impact on job performance. When machiavellianism scores are intermediate, organisational civic behaviour is found to be high, although consequences for both low and intermediate levels of machiavellianism were nearly same (Richard K. Dunhan 2008).

When their self-esteem is harmed, narcissistic people exhibit unproductive work behaviours including anger, anxiety, and injuring others. When job insecurity is high, narcissists report exhibiting more of this type of behaviour. They engage in excessive narcissistic behaviours to protect their individuality, which can take one of two forms. either a strong feeling of self-worth that ignores flaws or a weak sense of self-worth that ignores one's own assets. They are constantly on the lookout for methods to draw attention to themselves and claim credit for others. Despite their allegiance to their organisation, narcissists are committed to their own agenda, with little regard for the organization's goals, stakeholders' interests, or society as a whole (Duchon, D., & Burns, M.) (2008).

Psychopaths in positions of leadership make employees feel dissatisfied with the organization's outlooks that it does business in a socially acceptable manner, in an environmentally sustainable manner, and for the benefit of the community, country, and humanity. Corporate Psychopaths foster a culture of disengagement with employees, a disregard for doing a decent job, and a lack of respect for good work and unrewarded efforts. Researchers in the field of CSR cannot overlook the impact of individual manager characteristics. Clive R Bodd (2015) stated in a study that psychopaths make up only 1% of the general population that work in a business setting.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The goal of the current study is to determine the impact of Dark Triad Personality Traits on employee commitment to the organisation. Narcissism, psychopathy, and

Machiavellianism are three traits that make up the Dark Triad. It's an empirical study in which the impact of the Dark Triad on commitment is measured using a standardised questionnaire administered to 180 people.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The current study's goal is to explore how the Dark Triad Personality Trait affects employees' organisational commitment. Mean and cooreaction scores were computed to investigate the link.

Machiavellism has a greater value than mean for organisational commitment. As a result, Machiavellism and organisational dedication have a considerable negative association. Further evidence is provided by Ingo Zettler and Niklas Friedrich (2011), who show that Machiavellism is positively connected to self-related job commitment and negatively related to other types of work commitment, such as team and supervision dedication.

There is no correlation between narcissism and organisational dedication. The narcissistic narcissist, according to Schwartz (1987), only demonstrates devotion or involvement in work in order to make a favourable impression on the employer or others in positions of higher authority.

The relationship between psychopathy and organisational commitment is inversely proportional. It demonstrates that employees with a high level of organisational commitment have a low level of psychopathy. Organisation Commitment has a higher mean value than Psychopathy. Boddy, Clive R (2010) Employees that are psychopaths are organisation predators who mercilessly exploit others for personal benefit; they are completely dedicated to working for themselves rather than for others, which will influence their dedication to the company.

CONCLUSION

According to the findings of this study, there is a substantial negative association between Machiavellism and Organization Commitment. In the same way, there was a substantial negative link between the Psychopath and Organization Commitment, but no significant relationship between Organization Commitment and narcissism. It took a long time to evaluate all of the variables together, but it was crucial for understanding how personality traits influence organisational commitment.

Although there has been very little research done on the issue of The Effect of Dark Triad Personality Trait on Employee Commitment to the Organization, Even industrialised countries have scant information on the topic. As a result, a study like this in India is crucial. Employee commitment to the organisation is a problem that many developing countries confront, and studying the Dark Triad can help solve it. Counselors in the workplace can be extremely helpful in this situation. Employees with a low level of devotion to their jobs may be offered counselling sessions based on the results. It is necessary to create awareness among human resource professionals.

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